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Influence of Parenting Styles on the School Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of parenting styles on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study, a review of related literature was done to find gaps, prove and back up findings. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 47, 297 Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 588 students sampled from the population. The Parenting Styles and School Adjustment Questionnaire (PSSAQ) was developed and administered to gather data about students' school adjustment. A trial test was conducted on 50 students who were not part of the sample to test the reliability of the instrument. Data gathered was computed using Cronbach's Alpha and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.96. The questionnaire was made up of 2 main sections of A and B. Section A contained information about the questionnaire options and instructions, while section B was made of the items to be responded to. The section B had 4 subsections and 5 items under each subsection giving a total of 20 items. The questionnaire followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. The data were analyzed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed that; authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and neglectful parenting styles have influence on the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that; schools in collaboration with the Parents Teacher Association should organise guidance and counselling programs for parents to sensitise them on various parenting styles and their ramifications on academic adjustment of students.

Keywords: Parenting Styles, Authoritative Parenting, Authoritarian Parenting, Permissive Parenting, Neglectful Parenting and School Adjustment.

INTRODUCTION

Schools are institutions set up for the purpose of shaping students into desirable individuals of the society. Schools transmit into the students the values of the society and prepares them for the task of national development. Everything that goes on in the school environment is summarized as teaching and learning. The teaching-learning process is however, dependent on the student's adjustment to the school rules and regulations and the school's general environment and climate. As in every situation, students go through an adjustment process when they get into school, and they continue to adjust as they progress through the different stages of learning. Developing school-related behavior is crucial for school adjustment; following rules and establishing appropriate relationships with peers are developmental tasks that a student must perform.

According to Alao (2014), adjustment is the process of altering behaviour or affective response so as to reach a harmonious relationship with new or challenging environment, situation or person. It entails a modification of physical and psychological dispositions of an individual to be able to meet up with the demands and challenges of life. Adjustment simply implies the process of striking a balance between the needs of an individual and his environment.

School adjustment is the process of accustoming to the school environment by the students. It refers to the interaction between the students and all aspects related in the school environment. The length of this adjustment period differs from person to person. It is a process of interaction between the students and the whole environment, which is related with not only the physical adjustment but also the mental adjustment (George, 2020). Students with proper adjustment feel a sense of belongingness to their school. They feel comfortable, relaxed and secure, and do not feel over-anxious, fearful or upset. They obey the school rules and regulation and listen to the instructions, interact well with others, can manage their emotions and feeling in an acceptable manner. Such students have interest to learning and are motivated to take part in the extra co-curricular activities in the school (Margetts, 2015).

School adjustment implies students' ability to adhere to and abide by the school rules and regulations; it covers their respect for constituted authority which could be that of the prefects, class teachers, principal and other staff in the school community. The student's ability to exhibit discipline and obedience is key to their success in academics and other areas in the school. Children's abilities, skills, adjustment characteristics, and interpersonal environment underlie their school adjustment process. While school adjustment might be a requirement for success in school, the process starts from home and is heavily influenced by the students' upbringing which is a product of the parenting style.

Parenting style is a pattern of attitudes that parents exhibit toward the upbringing of their children (Tam, Chong, Kadirvelu & Khoo, 2012). According to Gawas (2021) the term parenting style refers to the different methods that parents take into consideration to develop the social behaviors of their children. Parenting styles are also defined as all behavior issued by parents about good parenting, and their perceptions about their behavior towards children. In addition to their awareness of the nature of the relationship between them and their children. There are different parenting styles distinguished by the level of demandingness and responsiveness exhibited by the parents. According to Shahlal, Isa and Kecek (2021) the types of parenting styles were introduced by Baumrind (1967). The author classified parenting styles into three; authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive. In 1983, Maccoby and Martin have extended the study of Baumrind (1967). As a result, Maccoby and Martin (1983) have introduced another type of parenting style which is known as neglectful or uninvolved (Shahlal, Isa & Kecek, 2021).

Authoritarian parenting style is often associated with a strict way of parenting and educating the child. This parenting style stresses more on a high level of child discipline (Baumrind, 1971). According to Darko and Gyasi (2019), the authoritarian parents shape, control, and evaluate the behaviour and attitudes of the child in accordance with a set standard of conduct, usually an absolute standard, theologically motivated and formulated by a higher authority. The parent value obedience as a virtue and favours punitive, forceful measures to curb self-will at points where the child's actions or beliefs conflict with what she thinks is right conduct. However, this parenting style will cause the child to not have high self-

confidence and do not dare to make any decisions on their own. Due to that, the child will be dependent and always expect the parents will help them in every situation. Moreover, there is possibility for the child to be a cheater as they want to avoid being punished (Morin, 2019).

The authoritative parent attempts to direct the child's activities but in a rational, issue-oriented manner. The parents encourage verbal give and take, share with the child the reasoning behind their policy, and solicit his objections when he refuses to conform. Both autonomous self-will and disciplined conformity are valued (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Authoritative parents are firm in educating the child but tend to be more flexible. According to Baumrind (1971), parents for this parenting style are easier to interact with the child in deciding. Parents who adopt this parenting style have a balance between responsiveness and demand (Saifuddin Abdullah, 2007). Just like authoritarian parents, authoritative parents also set rules for their child along with punishment if they fail to follow. However, authoritative parents will explain to the child the reasons for the rule and punishment which is been made (Shahlal, Isa & Kechek, 2021). Authoritative parenting style create more positive effect on a child. The child will be more courageous, independent, positive, and confident to face challenges in the future. The child will develop a good social relationship with others and a sense of trust can be enhanced.

Permissive parenting style is a form of parenting where the parents are relatively non-controlling, make few demands on their children, allow them to make their own decisions, and regulate their own behavior. The permissive parenting style refuses to impose rules and standards but allows children's self-regulation. Parents act in an acceptant and affirmative manner towards the child's impulses and desires without punitive actions (Uji, Sakamoto, Adachi & Kitamura, 2014). Such children have a high level of freedom with no restriction of any behaviors if there is no physical harm. In this parenting style, the parents do not demand anything and expect little from their children. The parent-children relationship is at the friendship level with few limits imposed (Berg, 2011). However, permissive parenting style can cause a child to acquire disciplinary problems as well as low academic achievement. It is believed that the adolescents which raised by this type of parenting style are typically immature in various psychosocial aspects (Baumrind, 1975). Besides, a child will also experience personality disorders such as becoming aggressive, rebellious, and like to dominate over something (Nazarudin, 2020). This may cause that a child often feel that their parents are only concerned about themselves, and their work compared to the child's affairs.

Neglectful or uninvolved parenting style is an undemanding and uncaring way of parenting a child. The idea of neglectful parenting style is identified by few parental demands, little communication and low responsiveness to their children. These parents usually disengage themselves from their children's life after fulfilling their basic needs. According to Williams and Sánchez (2012), uninvolved parents are self-involved or too busy, thus they can hardly provide the basic needs of food and shelter. They expect their children to take care of their own destiny. Parents of the parenting style show very little love, attention, mental and moral support, protection, and supervision to their children. Parents know very little about their children. It is because the parents do not spend much time with their child. However, based on Morin (2019), some parents who being neglectful over their child are often unintentionally. This may happen as the parents being too busy with their jobs. The child who raised by this type of parenting style often have problems and crisis with their parents. As the child could not spend much time together with their parents, there will be no mutual understanding between a child and the parents which cause the two parties of not having a close relationship. If the parents try to show their love towards the child, there will be a doubt in the heart of a child in valuing the love. The child who is been raised by this parenting style is always associated with low level of school performance and often causes behavior problem (Morin, 2019).

The role of parenting in children's education has become a central issue in educational policy and research. Research findings support the existence of a positive relationship between parenting styles and educational success, especially in the secondary school years (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Parents are considered as an imperative support system available to any child and seem to play a momentous role in the development of the child. Although the significance of family environment in the advancement of the

child cannot be ignored, the strongest factor influencing the development of the child is the style used by parents for their child's upbringing (Rahman, Begum & Nahar, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The researchers, like parents, counsellors and schools has a sincere interest in knowing and tackling the various problems affecting students' school adjustment and learning but the more the concern, the more the rate of failures in our secondary schools and students' maladjustment. This is so because, in today's context, schools are dealing with a large population of culturally deprived young-stars who mostly have stimulus malnutrition. In most cases, neglect by parents in the process of seeking for how to make ends means, lack of educational and recreational materials in childhood, autocratic parenting style and most often permissive attitude of parents, have not provided the motivational basis for a well-balanced social interaction and achievement in school work. The students are becoming progressively inadequate and alienated from the activities of the school. Most students in this category cope with such inadequacy by dropping out of school due to persistent failure or may be lured into examination malpractices, cultism, substance abuse, disruptive behaviour, noise making, late coming, truancy among others.

The researchers observed that students in the junior secondary school classes tend to be more obedient and law abiding in the school because of their age and maturity. Those in the senior secondary school classes however, because of their age and maturity tend to rebel and disrespect prefects and even teachers. Although not all of them, the researchers feel this could be influenced by how they are raised in their various homes, since everything starts there and it is also the primary agent of socialization. Therefore, the current study seeks to find out how senior secondary school students adjust to constituted authority in school as related to the type of parents they have at home. This group of students is chosen because they tend to be matured in age and reasoning and are more prone to feel the need to do otherwise than told. However, with different parenting styles affecting how students are likely to respond to constituted authority, the aim of this study is to find out differences in respect to authority based on the parenting style dominant in a student's household.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of parenting styles on the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of authoritative parenting style on the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. Investigate the influence of authoritarian parenting style on the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. Determine the influence of permissive parenting style on the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.
4. Determine the influence of neglectful parenting style on the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered to guide the study:

1. How does authoritative parenting style influence the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. How does authoritarian parenting style influence the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. How does permissive parenting style influence the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?
4. How does neglectful parenting style influence the school adjustment of Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was made up of all students in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. The population of the study comprised 47,297 Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 588 students. The Parenting Styles and School Adjustment Questionnaire (PSSAQ) was developed and administered to gather data about students' school adjustment. The questionnaire was made up of 2 main sections of A and B. Section A contained information about the questionnaire options and instructions, while section B was made of the items to be responded to. The section B had 4 subsections and 5 items under each subsection giving a total of 20 items. A trial test was conducted on 50 students who were not part of the sample to test the reliability of the instrument. Data gathered was computed using Cronbach's Alpha and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.96. The questionnaire followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. The data were analyzed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: *How does authoritative parenting style influence the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Authoritative Parenting Style on the School Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	In the house, my parents do not feel that I need to obey rules and regulations of behaviour simply because someone in authority had established them and I feel like that about the school as well.	183	245	80	80	2.90	.992	Accepted
2	As I was growing up, I knew what my parents expected of me in my family, but I also felt free to discuss those expectations with them when I felt that they were unreasonable so I complain before I obey in school.	281	213	43	51	3.23	.920	Accepted
3	My parents respect me and I also respect them, I expect same from my mates, prefects and teachers in school.	244	259	54	31	3.22	.819	Accepted
4	As I was growing up, my parents seldom gave me expectations and guidelines for my behaviour so I like doing as I feel is right even in school.	200	288	59	41	3.10	.843	Accepted
5	When I was growing up my parents did what the children in the family wanted when making family decisions I wish it was so in the school too.	188	234	109	57	2.94	.994	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.078$ SD= .9136								Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.90, 3.23, 3.22, 3.10, and 2.94 with corresponding standard deviations of .992, .920, .819, .843, and .994 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.078 with the cluster standard deviation of .9136 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that authoritative parenting

style has influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *How does authoritarian parenting style influence the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Authoritarian Parenting Style on the School Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	I do not have any problem with obeying school rules and regulations because my parents are quite strict.	440	122	26	0	3.70	.545	Accepted
7	As I was growing up, my parents did not allow me to question any decision they had made so I am used to obeying without complain, even in school.	219	277	66	26	3.17	.796	Accepted
8	As I was growing up, my parents directed the activities and decisions of the children in the family through reasoning and discipline it feels same in school.	245	166	91	86	2.97	1.076	Accepted
9	My parents had always felt that more force should be used by parents in order to get their children to behave the way they are supposed to, this is what the teachers do and I feel it is okay.	206	304	65	13	3.20	.715	Accepted
10	While I was growing up my parents controlled everything in the house, I wish the school could be like that too.	203	242	91	52	3.01	.925	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}=3.21$ SD=.8114								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.70, 3.17, 2.97, 3.20, and 3.01 with corresponding standard deviations of .545, .796, 1.076, .715, and .925 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.21 with the cluster standard deviation of .8114 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that authoritarian parenting style has influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *How does permissive parenting style influence the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Permissive Parenting Style on the School Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	My parents let me do as I please in the house but the school causes me discomfort with too many rules and regulations.	231	239	28	90	3.04	1.026	Accepted
12	The school forces me to obey rules and regulations while my parents let me do anything I like in the house.	151	356	10	71	3.00	.871	Accepted
13	I do not always ask for permission to do things in the house, but in school it is a different case.	286	207	29	66	3.21	.970	Accepted
14	The prefects and teachers have problems with me sometimes because they try to act like my parents when they are not.	145	340	35	68	2.96	.876	Accepted
15	I got into a brawl with a prefect one time because he wanted to force me to do what he wanted. Even my parents do not force me.	234	211	22	121	2.95	1.122	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}=3.032$ SD=.973								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 3.04, 3.00, 3.21, 2.96, and 2.95 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.026, .871, .970, .876, and 1.122 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.032 with the cluster standard deviation of .973 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that permissive parenting style has influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 4: *How does neglectful parenting style influence the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Table 4: Analysis of Influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on the School Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
16	My parents treat me like an adult in the house I wish the teachers would do same in school.	196	241	101	50	2.99	.920	Accepted
17	I have never been punished in the house, so I don't see why I should be punished in school.	477	85	26	0	3.77	.517	Accepted
18	My parents tolerate me the way I am but the school makes it difficult for me to be myself.	266	246	51	25	3.28	.795	Accepted
19	I have my way about things at home because my parents are lenient with me and my siblings but my teachers and prefects are too strict.	266	205	63	54	3.16	.950	Accepted
20	My parents understand that I know what is wrong and right so they don't bother correcting me I wish it was so in school.	251	268	10	59	3.21	.896	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation \bar{X}= 3.282 SD= .8156								Accepted

Table 4 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 16 to 20 are 2.99, 3.77, 3.28, 3.16, and 3.21 with corresponding standard deviations of .920, .517, .795, .950, and .896 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.282 with the cluster standard deviation of .8156 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that neglectful parenting style has influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions for ease of reading and comprehension.

The first finding of the study revealed that authoritative parenting style has significant influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. This implies that the authoritative parenting style which is also called democratic parenting style influences students' adjustment. This adjustment is psychosocial, as it affects how they relate with others in school and also how it affects their emotions, feelings, attitudes and cognitions. In the data gathered, more than 50% of the respondents ticked strongly agreed and agreed to the statements; "My parents respect me and I also respect them, I expect same from my mates, prefects and teachers in school", "When I was growing up my parents did what the children in the family wanted when making family decisions I wish it was so in the school too." While some of the respondents disagreed to the statements, a majority of the responses were skewed to the positive. The authoritative parenting style is democratic in nature and avers the offspring an opportunity of airing their views about decisions taken in the house. From literature, it is the most recommended parenting style and as the name implies, it favours and

promotes some level of equality between parents and offspring. However, it influences how such offspring view and obey rules, regulations and constituted authority within and outside the home. Because of the democratic nature of the home environment, this set of students tend to question the basis for certain rules and are quick to request for explanations as to why they are expected to conform. This attitude affects their school adjustment. Corroboratively, Njoku and Akaninwor-David (2019) in a study about influence of parenting styles on social adjustment of students with disability found that authoritative parenting style had a significantly higher prediction on social adjustment of students with physical disability than other parenting styles. Perez-Gramaje, Garcia, Reyes, Serra, and Garcia (2018) also found that the authoritative parenting style which is characterized by warmth and strictness had better outcomes in curbing aggressiveness among adolescents.

The second finding of the study revealed that authoritarian parenting style has significant influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. This implies that the authoritarian parenting style influences modifications in how students participate in classes and activities. It affects the process of students accustoming to the school environment. This parenting style does not promote offspring having a say in decisions that concern their lives and the family. It however interferes with proper psychosocial development and adjustment in school and other spheres of life. Corroboratively, Omotoso, Oyetoro and Banjoko (2020) in a study found that parenting styles had significant influence on the social adjustment problems of students. This is notable because the process of adjusting socially in the school environment is part of academic adjustment. Perez-Gramaje *et al.*, (2018) found that the authoritarian parenting style was did not have good outcomes in the socialization of adolescents.

The third finding of the study revealed that permissive parenting style has significant influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. This implies that the permissive parenting style influenced the adaptation and performance of students in schools. More than 70% of the respondents agreed that while they were growing up, their parents felt that in a well-run home the children should have their way with the family as often as the parents do. This attitude helped to shaped their assertiveness and development. Being a typical characteristic of the permissive parenting style, these parents set very few rules and boundaries and they are reluctant to enforce rules. These indulgent parents are warm and indulgent but they do not like to say no or disappoint their children. The respondents agreed that their parents provided this sort of atmosphere for them while they were growing up. However, this atmosphere contrasts with what is obtainable in schools and they averred that it affected their school adjustment. Similarly, Muza and Muhammad (2020) found in their study on the effect of parenting styles on social adjustment of secondary school students in Kebbi State, Nigeria that parenting styles have significant effect on social adjustment of senior secondary school students. Alika, Akanni and Akanni (2016) also found that permissive parenting style did not correlate with psychological distress. These findings suggest that higher levels of control, which is characteristic of both authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles, may be a critical factor in the development of psychological distress. However, authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles significantly correlated inversely and directly with psychological distress in adolescents.

The fourth finding of the study revealed that neglectful parenting style has significant influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. This implies that parents' non-indulgent attitude towards their children influence how they interact with others in the school environment. Neglectful parents do not set firm boundaries or high standards. They are indifferent to their children's needs and uninvolved in their lives. These uninvolved parents may have mental issues themselves such as depression, or physical abuse or child neglect when they were kids. More than 50% of the respondents averred that while they were growing up their parents did not care about how they acted at home. The existence of an influence of parenting styles on academic adjustment of students coincides with the findings of Muza and Muhammad (2020) whom found in their study that; parenting styles have significant effect on social adjustment of senior secondary school students. They also recommended that since parenting styles effect the social adjustment of students, parents should

endeavour to adopt a style such as the democratic one that ensures or guarantees the development of some measure of positive self-concept, self-confidence, and self-esteem in the students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that parenting styles have significant influence on the school adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Schools in collaboration with the Parents Teacher Association should organise guidance and counselling programs for parents to sensitise them on various parenting styles and their ramifications on academic adjustment of students.
2. Since parenting styles affect the school and social adjustment of students, parents should endeavour to adopt a style such as the authoritative one that ensures or guarantees the development of some measure of psychosocial development.
3. Schools should create an enabling environment that would provide the students with warmth and nurturance, set academic expectations of maturity and control to help improve their adjustment.
4. Counsellors may help parents gain the knowledge and skills necessary to support their adolescents to fulfill their psychological needs.

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